

VALIDATION OF POSSIBLE APPLICATIONS OF FLAKE LAMINATES FOR RECYCLING OF PA6-CF PRODUCTION SCRAP

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ABSTRACT

To facilitate the future application of mechanically shredded production scrap of polyamide 6-carbon fiber (PA6-CF), a comprehensive assessment of its potential use cases is essential. As a first step, the influence of selected process parameters on the processing behavior and quality of the resulting laminates was systematically investigated. Based on 3-point bending and tensile tests possible applications of flake laminates with structural or visual requirements are looked at and compared to sheet molding laminates out of chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (SM-CTT). The results indicate that the mechanical properties of the recycled PA6-CF flake laminates are comparable to those of SM-CTT materials, suggesting analogous fields of application. Despite minor surface defects, a largely smooth surface finish was attainable. From an ecological standpoint, a significant advantage of this recycling approach is the direct reutilization of production scrap without the need for fiber-matrix separating or the addition of external materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lightweight construction is a key technology for enhancing resource and energy efficiency across various industries, particularly in the transportation sector. In automotive engineering, reducing mass-dependent driving resistances contributes significantly to the reduction of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. [1] Fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPs; if carbon-fiber-reinforced: CFRPs), in particular thermoplastic-based variants (tFRPs), offer high potential for lightweight design due to their excellent specific mechanical properties. Compared to thermoset systems, tFRPs enable shorter processing times, lower material costs and improved end-of-life recyclability. [2, 3]

Especially organosheets, a semi-finished tFRP, offer significant weight-saving potential. Organosheets are typically manufactured in flat sheet form through consolidation processes and later shaped into complex parts using thermoforming or pressforming techniques. Despite careful planning, the production with organosheets often generates considerable scrap, particularly in high-volume processes. [4, 5]

This paper investigates a strategy for the reutilization of production scrap from thermoplastic composite manufacturing. The aim is to evaluate the material and structural performance of reprocessed scrap material and to assess its suitability for reintegration into functional components. By establishing methods for the reuse of tFRP production waste, the overall sustainability and material efficiency of composite-based lightweight systems can be significantly improved.

Traditional recycling approaches for composite waste include mechanical processing, thermal recycling or the separation of individual components through solvolysis. After the mechanical recycling of thermoplastics, shredded waste can be reused via processes such as injection molding or extrusion. However, the original fiber length is significantly reduced, leading to a decrease in the mechanical properties of the recycled material. [6, 7]

An innovative and promising recycling alternative takes advantage of the thermoplastic matrix and its re-meltability and re-moldability – fibers and matrix are not separated. Because the production waste can vary greatly in size, the approach starts by segmenting tFRP scrap into cm-sized more manageable pieces, called flakes. In the next step the flakes can be consolidated into a semi-finished product by evenly distributing, heating them above melting point and compressing them. The semi-finished product can be manufactured like organosheets by thermoforming or pressforming techniques. This method facilitates the creation of a new type of laminate that combines material and energy efficiency, making it suitable for applications with moderate mechanical property requirements. [7] This not only undermines the ecological and economic benefits of lightweight construction but also presents a largely untapped secondary resource.

2 PROCEDURE/METHOD

The semi-finished laminate, a consolidated panel, could be used in two different use cases of thermoforming: applications with structural requirements and visible parts. A simple isothermal manufacturing process is looked at to reduce process complexity. To ensure a stable thermoforming process the process conditions for the semi-finished product must be evaluated. Based on differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Design of Experiments, the main process parameters for the isothermal manufacturing process including pre-heating temperature, pre-heating duration, press force, cavity temperature and press time are varied. This is to analyze the effect of the parameters on the mechanical properties. Three-point-bending tests are carried out to analyze the mechanical properties. A low bending stress and flexural modulus should indicate insufficient consolidation. Consolidation was also assessed visually and qualitatively based on surface continuity and absence of visible delamination. An additional qualitative assessment was performed using tap test, in which the acoustic response of the sheet was evaluated. A high-pitched, metallic sound is indicative of proper consolidation, while a dull sound may suggest internal defects or insufficient consolidation. Goal is a flake laminate which is fully consolidated and could reach structural or visual requirements.

After finding the best process parameters, the mechanical properties of the process are analyzed and compared to traditional materials like SM-CTT. In the second application for visible parts the focus is on fiber cohesion and surface defects, evaluating whether the panel could meet visual requirements.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIAGTIONS

3.1 Materials

The experimental procedure involves using PA6-CF tape with a fiber mass content of 60 wt.% from Envalior GmbH (Germany) as the virgin material, which is consolidated, and chopped into flakes measuring 6 mm to 14 mm in equivalent diameter. According to the tape manufacturer, the tape properties are the following:

Properties	Unit	Typical Data	Test Method
Density	(kg/m ³)	1450	ISO 1183
Fiber content (V/V)	(%)	49	ISO 11667
Tensile modulus – 0°	(GPa)	135	ISO 527-4
Stress at break – 0°	(MPa)	1700	ISO 527-4
Strain at break – 0°	(%)	1.4	ISO 527-4
Melting temperature	(°C)	220	ISO 11357-1

Table 1: Properties of the PA6-CF tape according to the datasheet.

Figure 1 shows the PA6-CF tape after consolidating and chopping in the form of flakes. This material has a three-dimensional, voluminous, loose structure.

Figure 1: Chopped flakes.

3.2 Manufacturing

The isothermal process includes two main manufacturing steps:

The series of pictures in Figure 2 illustrates the manufacturing process.

Figure 2: Manufacturing process of flake laminates by isothermal process.

For pre-heating, the tFRP-flakes are evenly distributed between two metal sheets. To contain the flakes and prevent material leakage during pressing, a 2 mm thick metal frame is inserted between the sheets. This also leads to equal sheet thicknesses. To enhance demoldability one side of each sheet is lined with polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE)-film. The stack is heated in a convection oven of the company Nabertherm GmbH (Germany), type TR 240. In order to identify suitable process conditions for pre-heating, the relevant parameters were systematically varied as follows:

- Pre-heating temperatures: 225 °C, 250 °C, 275 °C
- Pre-heating duration: 10 min, 12.5 min, 15 min, 17.5 min, 20 min

The weight of the covering metal sheet compresses the CFRP flakes, resulting in a pre-compacted structure. After completing the pre-heating cycle, the stack is manually transferred to the pressing tool with a planar mold cavity. The size of the cavity measures 350 mm x 300 mm. Both halves of the mold are equipped with electrically heated cartridges for temperature control. Consolidation is carried out using a servo-motorized screw press (Synchropress GmbH (Germany), type: 1M-300) under the following process parameters:

- Forming pressure: 20 bar, 40 bar, 80 bar
- Cavity temperature: 80 °C, 100 °C, 120 °C
- Holding time: 30 s, 60 s, 120 s

The forming pressure p is set using the known area of the cavity A and the set pressing force F (cf. Equation 1).

$$p = F/A \quad (1)$$

After passing the holding time the press returns to the starting position and the stack can be ejected manually.

3.3 Sample preparation and test methods

Mechanical properties are evaluated through three-point bending and tensile tests, following DIN EN ISO 14125 and DIN EN ISO 527-4 standards, respectively. Both geometries can be cut out of the produced flake-laminate sheets by waterjet cutting. For tensile tests the specimen measures 250 mm x 25 mm. Three-point bending samples measure 100 mm x 15 mm. Since PA6 tends to absorb water, the specimens were dried at 80 °C for 5 hours in a climate chamber and afterwards conditioned at 23 °C and 50 % relative humidity for 8 hours. Tests are performed on a servo-electric (type: Criterion C45.105) universal testing machine from MTS Systems Corporation (USA) with a testing speed of 2 mm/min. To assess potential anisotropy, specimens are extracted in both the 0° and 90° directions.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Influence of process parameters on degree of consolidation and mechanical properties

The pre-heating temperature has a significant impact on the degree of consolidation and resulting mechanical properties of the PA6-CF flake laminates. At a pre-heating temperature of 225 °C, approximately 5 °C above the peak melting point determined via DSC, insufficient consolidation was observed. The produced laminates were fragmented and unsuitable for mechanical testing. Increasing the pre-heating temperature to 250 °C improved consolidation significantly, as indicated by a smoother surface appearance and enhanced structural integrity. Further increasing the temperature to 275 °C yielded to no noticeable differences in surface quality and mechanical properties compared to 250 °C, as confirmed by three-point bending tests (bending stress: (102.52 ± 19.23) MPa vs. (116.34 ± 22.11) MPa; flexural modulus: (10812.64 ± 1401.88) MPa vs. (10614.54 ± 990.77) MPa).

In a subsequent experimental series, the influence of pre-heating duration was investigated. A pre-heating duration of 10 minutes resulted in poor consolidation with extensive surface defects and fragmentation. Extending the duration to 12.5, 15 and 17.5 minutes led to notable improvements (bending stress: (103.64 ± 13.87) MPa, (102.52 ± 19.23) MPa, (165.95 ± 16.18) MPa; flexural modulus (8820.65 ± 1245.19) MPa, (10812.64 ± 1401.88) MPa, (12556.67 ± 1930.39) MPa), indicating more complete consolidation. The characteristic metallic sound during tap testing further supported this observation. However, further extending the duration to 20 minutes, caused a decline in mechanical performance (bending stress: (120.79 ± 25.14) MPa; flexural modulus: (11138.02 ± 4250.62) MPa). Since thermal degradation at this temperature and time frame is unlikely, the decrease in properties is attributed to extended transfer durations between oven and press, which may have led to a significant drop in laminate temperature before pressing.

The press force also influenced the consolidation outcome. At 250 °C pre-heating temperature, a forming pressure of 20 bar was insufficient to ensure complete consolidation, resulting in visibly defective surfaces. Pressures of ≥ 40 bar were required to obtain nearly defect-free laminate surfaces at this temperature. No significant mechanical differences were observed between samples pressed at 40 bar and 80 bar (bending stress: (102.52 ± 19.23) MPa vs. (97.19 ± 11.26) MPa; flexural modulus: (10812.64 ± 1401.88) MPa vs. (9733.37 ± 647.42) MPa). At elevated pre-heating temperatures, a pressure of 20 bar was found to be adequate.

The pressing tool enables a slow, controlled cooling of the laminate, which promotes crystallization and improves mechanical performance. However, variation in temperature did not lead to significant differences in three-point bending properties between 80 °C and 100 °C temperature (bending stress: (114.41 ± 24.34) MPa vs. (102.52 ± 19.23) MPa; flexural modulus: (9415.86 ± 1899.78) MPa vs. (10812.64 ± 1401.88) MPa). At 120 °C both values declined by approximately 50 %, indicating suboptimal cooling conditions.

A holding time of 60 seconds in the press yielded the best mechanical performance (bending stress: (102.52 ± 19.23) MPa; flexural modulus: (10812.64 ± 1401.88) MPa). A shorter duration of 30 seconds led to lower values (bending stress: (82.68 ± 13.37) MPa; flexural modulus: (7454.42 ± 1242.22) MPa), while an extended time of 120 seconds show no further benefit (bending stress: (80.66 ± 21.64) MPa; flexural modulus: (8133.93 ± 1166.30) MPa).

The results underline the importance of carefully controlled pre-heating temperature and duration and indicate them as the two main controlling process parameters of the whole process. Heat loss during manual transfer between oven and press – characteristic of this isothermal process – can result in suboptimal consolidation and surface defects, as the material temperature may fall below the ideal processing range. To counteract this the pre-heating temperature must be set above peak melting point indicated by DSC.

Based on these results, the following process parameters should at least be achieved to ensure sufficient consolidation and mechanical performance for the investigated material:

- Pre-heating temperature: > 250 °C
- Pre-heating duration: > 17.5 minutes
- Forming pressure: > 25 bar
- Cavity temperature: 100 °C
- Press holding time: 60 s

Initial trials were conducted using reduced amount of flake material compared to the amount used in the subsequent production of full-sized laminate sheets. To evaluate the internal heat-up behavior of larger flake stacks, a thermocouple was embedded centrally during pre-heating. At an oven setpoint of 250 °C, the core of the stack required more than 65 minutes to reach the target temperature of 250 °C. This suggests that prior specimens processed with lower flake mass may not have fully reached processing temperature, potentially explaining earlier inconsistencies. By increasing the oven temperature to 275 °C this duration was reduced to 23.5 minutes, while at 290 °C the target temperature was achieved after 17.5 minutes.

These findings demonstrate the relatively slow heat transfer into the flake material. To ensure that the flakes remain above melting temperature during transfer to the mold and subsequent consolidation, the oven temperature and pre-heating duration must be adjusted.

Based on the results of these thermal evaluations, the process parameters in Table 2 were selected to produce flake laminates for three-point bending and tensile tests. The forming pressure was maintained at 25 bar, the cavity temperature was set to 100 °C, and a consistent holding time of 60 s was applied in all cases.

Sample	Pre-heating temperature (°C)	Pre-heating duration (min)
275°C_24min	275	24
275°C_29min	275	29
290°C_19min	290	19
300°C_19min	300	19

Table 2: Pre-heating temperatures and durations for the manufacturing process of different samples.

4.1 Mechanical properties in comparison to similar laminates

The processed sheets have a shiny and nearly defect-free surface and a metallic sound which indicates sufficient consolidation. They would be suitable for visual applications. The investigation of mechanical properties will show if the sheets can also be used in structural parts with mechanical requirements.

The mechanical characterization of the PA6-CF flake laminates was conducted via three-point bending and tensile testing. A comparison of specimens oriented in 0° and 90° direction revealed no statistically significant anisotropy, suggesting that the laminates exhibit quasi-isotropic behavior. As a result, test data are presented independent of extraction direction.

Figure 3 illustrates the average bending stress and flexural modulus values obtained for various processing parameters (cf. Table 2).

Figure 3: Average bending stress and flexural modulus of consolidated PA6-CF flake laminates.

The flexural modulus ranges from 11426.07 MPa (290°C_19min) to 14623.23 MPa (275°C_24min) with standard deviations between 1470.71 MPa and 2584.05 MPa. Notably, samples processed at an oven temperature of 275 °C with varying pre-heating durations yielded nearly identical flexural moduli within the margin of experimental uncertainty. Laminates processed at 290 °C and 300 °C with shorter pre-heating durations (19 minutes) achieve comparable modulus values. The relatively high standard deviation is attributed to process-related fluctuations, particularly variable transfer times between oven and press. Because of this instability and a slow heat transfer into the flake material the small changes in temperature or pre-heating duration have little to no significant impact on the flexural moduli.

Bending stress values vary between 89.17 MPa (300°C_19min) and 119.52 MPa (275°C_24min) with standard deviations from 19.44 MPa to 31.13 MPa. Across all variants, the bending stress results remain at a comparable level, reinforcing the hypothesis that inconsistent transfer times may have led to temporary temperature drops below the optimal consolidation window.

For reference, the flexural modulus of pure PA6, as specified in the material data sheet [8] of the material used in [9], is 1961 MPa which is approximately one-sixth of the values obtained for the flake laminates. In contrast, a PA6-CF with a similar fiber volume fraction exhibits a flexural modulus of 98112.4 MPa [10]. In comparison the flake laminates reach approximately 14,9 % of the flexural modulus of virgin continuous fiber composite, making them suitable for applications with moderate mechanical requirements.

Table 3 summarizes the tensile test results for PA6-CF flake laminates and compares them with reference materials, including pure PA6, SM-CTT with similar fiber volume content and the virgin continuous PA6-CF tape. The tensile modulus could only be determined for the 275°C_29min test series, as the slopes of the linear elastic regions in the other specimens exhibited significant variability, preventing a consistent evaluation.

Material	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Stress at break (MPa)	Strain at break (%)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
PA6-CF flake laminates				
275°C_24min	-	14.80 ± 9.32	0.01 ± 0.003	16.96 ± 9.45
275°C_29min	42.84 ± 3.64	23.09 ± 10.32	1.56 ± 1.1	31.46 ± 6.94
290°C_19min	-	27.47 ± 7.46	0.01 ± 0.002	27.75 ± 7.2
300°C_19min	-	22.97 ± 11.91	0.01 ± 0.003	26.84 ± 9.26
References				
Pure PA6 [11]	52000	-	28.70	28.70
SM-CTT (3t) (V/V=52.4 %) [9]	33.2 ± 2.9	-	0.9 ± 0.1	259.6 ± 39.1
PA6-CF tape (0°) [12]	135000	1700	1.4	1910

Table 3: Average mechanical properties for PA6-CF samples with different pre-heating temperature and duration and references from literature.

The highest mechanical performance among the flake laminates was achieved with a pre-heating regime of 275 °C for 29 minutes. The observed scatter in mechanical data is likely a result of uncontrolled variations in transfer time.

The tensile modulus of the flake laminates exceeded that of the SM-CTT reference, indicating their suitability as a replacement in applications where stiffness is a primary design criterion. However, the tensile strength and strain-at-break values fell significantly short of those achieved by continuous fiber-reinforced PA6-CF tape due to the inherently random fiber orientation in the flake structure. This structural limitation reduces the ability of the fiber phase to effectively carry axial load, which is reflected in the lower mechanical performance metrics.

The 275°C_29min reach roughly half of the values as SM-CTT and PA6-CF tape at strain at break when considering the high standard deviation. The tensile strength of the flake laminates was comparable to neat PA6 and reached approximately one-tenth of the SM-CTT reference. Despite this, the performance enhancement relative to the matrix alone demonstrates the reinforcing effect of the flakes and underscores the viability of this material for cost-sensitive, less demanding applications.

The mechanical properties show that some values are higher than pure PA6 and similar to SM-CTT. The PA6-CF tape has, as could be expected, better mechanical properties. Concluding that PA6-CF flake laminates are recommendable for visual applications or applications with medium to low standards on mechanical properties.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the feasibility of manufacturing PA6-CF flake laminates via an isothermal compression molding process using recycled material. The mechanical characterization revealed that, despite their randomly oriented microstructure, the laminates exhibit quasi-isotropic behavior and provide significantly enhanced stiffness compared to pure PA6. Although they fall short of the mechanical performance achieved by continuous or chopped fiber-reinforced tapes (e.g., SM-CTT or virgin PA6-CF), their performance is sufficient for structural applications with low to moderate mechanical demands, as well as for purely visual or semi-structural components as an intermediate layer or filling material.

The findings suggest that flake laminates offer a sustainable alternative to more resource-intensive fiber composites, particularly in contexts where full structural load-bearing capacity is not critical.

Overall, the study highlights the potential of mechanically recycled FRP composites in lightweight design and resource-efficient component production, supporting circular economy principles within tFRP processing.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Candela, G. Sandrini, M. Gadola, D. Chindamo, and P. Magri, "Lightweighting in the automotive industry as a measure for energy efficiency: Review of the main materials and methods," (in eng), *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 8, e29728, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29728.
- [2] AVK, Industrievereinigung Verstärkte Kunststoffe, *Handbuch Faserverbundkunststoffe/Composites: Grundlagen, Verarbeitung, Anwendungen*, 4th ed. Wiesbaden: Springer Vieweg, 2013.
- [3] R. Stewart, "Thermoplastic composites — recyclable and fast to process," *Reinforced Plastics*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 22–28, 2011, doi: 10.1016/S0034-3617(11)70073-X.
- [4] J. P. Snudden, C. Ward, and K. Potter, "Reusing automotive composites production waste," *Reinforced Plastics*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 20–27, 2014, doi: 10.1016/S0034-3617(14)70246-2.
- [5] P. K. Mallick, "Thermoplastics and thermoplastic–matrix composites for lightweight automotive structures," in *Materials, Design and Manufacturing for Lightweight Vehicles*: Elsevier, 2010, pp. 174–207.
- [6] C. Capela, S. E. Oliveira, J. Pestana, and J. Ferreira, "Effect of fiber length on the mechanical properties of high dosage carbon reinforced," *Procedia Structural Integrity*, vol. 5, pp. 539–546, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.prostr.2017.07.159.
- [7] S. M. Aldosari *et al.*, "Mechanical Recycling of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer in a Circular Economy," (in eng), *Polymers*, vol. 16, no. 10, 2024, doi: 10.3390/polym16101363.
- [8] M-Base Engineering + Software GmbH, *Material Data Center | Datasheet KOPA® KN177N*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.materialdatacenter.com/ms/en/Kopa/Kolon/KOPA%C2%AE+KN177N/43c4cab9/1395> (accessed: Jul. 8 2025).
- [9] Y. Wan, H. Suganuma, and J. Takahashi, "Effects of fabrication processes and tape thickness on tensile properties of chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics," *Composites Communications*, vol. 22, p. 100434, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.coco.2020.100434.
- [10] ORIBI Composites, *Carbon Fiber/PA6: (CF/PA6)*. [Online]. Available: <https://oribicomposites.com/oribicomposites/wp-content/uploads/sites/9/MKT-1006-Carbon-Fiber-PA6-Data-Sheet.pdf> (accessed: Jul. 8 2025).
- [11] H. J. An, J. S. Kim, K.-Y. Kim, D. Y. Lim, and D. H. Kim, "Mechanical and thermal properties of long carbon fiber-reinforced polyamide 6 composites," *Fibers Polym*, vol. 15, no. 11, pp. 2355–2359, 2014, doi: 10.1007/s12221-014-2355-5.
- [12] Celanese Materials Database, *CELSTRAN® CFR-TP PA6 CF60-03: CELESTRAN® CFR-TP*.